

SPECIFIC NAMES IN MOVLUD SULEYMANLI'S NOVEL "KOCH"

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After people began to form as a social being and to develop language and thus communication, they gave names to each other, to the objects they lived in, to the animals and birds they hunted and tamed, to natural and divine forces, to the plants and fruits they used for food, and so on. As their knowledge of life and nature expanded, such names also increased. Over time, some of the names became specialized and specifically indicated the named object, concept, or person, so they were accepted in linguistics under the term "proper names." Proper names are the object of study of onomastics, a branch of linguistics. In fiction, writers use proper names to name a work, a place or institution in the work, or individuals. Sometimes, the author expresses a certain symbolic meaning through a proper name. Azerbaijani writer Movlud Suleymanli did not choose proper names by chance in his most famous novel, "Koch" (Migration). The article studies proper names in the literary language of the author's novel "Koch".

Keywords: name, proper names, personal names, onomastics, onomastic unit, Movlud Suleymanli, novel "Koch", literary language, lexicon.

Introduction

Since ancient times, people have simply given names to objects they see in the world and to concepts they cannot see. According to the conclusion reached by researchers: "Everything has a name in language. Without names, it would be impossible to select people, all living beings, objects and events, as well as various geographical objects, and to distinguish them from each other" [6]. As civilization developed, as humans began to study nature and other people, naming also developed, and thus proper names began to be used to name people, geographical and cosmic objects, animals, and various material and cultural household items. Proper names are the subject of study of onomastics, a branch of linguistics. "Onomastics" is a Greek word meaning "the art of naming."

In the history of mankind, language has always been a means of communication. It has been possible for people to communicate with other people living in the same time and place, or with people who existed in another time and place, precisely through language. Oral literature, which is passed down from language to language and names centuries, and written literature, which connects centuries, make communication possible for people who do not live in the same time or place. As we have mentioned earlier, proper names, that is, onomastic units, are considered a reflection of historical memory in modern language: "Proper names are carriers of important ethnographic and cultural-historical information" [3]. "Each onomastic unit has strong and clear national characteristics in the language" [5].

The article studies the specific names used in the novel "Koch" by the representative of the famous 60s generation of Azerbaijani literature, People's Writer Movlud Suleymanli. The late writer is a prominent representative of Azerbaijani literature. Every line and every sentence he wrote carries deep meanings. The author, with his rich language and content, has given both Azerbaijani literature and the modern Azerbaijani language a treasure.

Main body

Movlud Suleymanli was born on March 18, 1943, in the village of Jujakand, West Azerbaijan (now Armenia). His father was killed in World War II, and Movlud was raised by his mother. In 1962, he entered the Philology Department of Azerbaijan State University and graduated in 1967.

He worked for a while as an editor, screenwriter, and manager in various television, radio, and magazines. The main factors characterizing the literary activity of M. Suleymanli, who began his creative work with poems, are that the history, ethnography, moral and ethical values, and patriotic feelings of the people he belongs to are in the foreground in his works. The writer, who studied and revived the millennial culture and mythology of the Oghuz Turks from scratch and used it as the cornerstone of his art, published stories one after another in the second half of the 1970s. Starting from the 1980s, the writer turned more to the novel genre.

The writer's novels "Koch", "Ceviz kurdu", "Ses" are considered an important step in the development of modern Azerbaijani novel studies. "Koch", the first of three complementary novels by Mevlud Suleymanli, is written in the mythological way of thinking of the ancient Turks living in the geography of Azerbaijan. "In conveying artistic ideas, onomastic names are distinguished from ordinary words due to their stylistic function" [4]. The author chose each name for a special purpose. It is as if the migration described by Suleymanli describes to the reader the migration of life and thought of those who migrated to and from this geography. If we start the analysis from the title of the work, we will see that this migration is the migration of the Karakall family, this migration is the migration of a people who have periodically strayed from their history and traditions. The prominent poet Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh wrote about his work "Koch": "This novel is, above all, an artistic ethnography of the history, customs and traditions of the paths our people have traveled for hundreds of years, and of their nomadic spirit" [8].

The artistic language of Movlud Suleymanli is very rich. The words flowing from his pen seem to sing a song, forcing the reader to listen to this song. He skillfully used proper names. "The poetic experience of prominent writers shows that the correspondence of onomastic units to stylistic moments causes them to make a deep impression in the word environment. The successful position of those words in the text immediately makes the artistic purpose of the word artist feel" [1]. The author's work "Koch" is rich in anthroponyms, toponyms, zoonyms and cosmonyms. In total, about 80 proper names are used in the work.

"Writers widely use personal names for various stylistic purposes, to reveal the characterological features of the image, to increase emotionality, to create comedy, humor, by deliberately distorting names, using them in accordance with folk etymology, etc. purposes" [2]. In linguistics, the field that studies personal names is called anthroponymics. "Anthroponymics studies the formation, development, and improvement of human names, in short, the past and present state of names" [7]. In this work, all the people, geographical places, and animals named by the author seem to reveal their characters through their names. Although the events in the work take place at the beginning of the 20th century, we read the story of the migration of the ancient Karakalle clan that came to these lands over time. This migration is the migration of the ancient Oghuz, the ancient Turk.

In the novel, the names of people are arranged according to the flow of history, according to the author's purposeful choice. The Oghuz bride, Hürü nene, who looks after two orphan boys, embodies the ancient Turkic image of motherhood, tenderness, and care. Not only **Hürü nənə** – grandma Huru, but the names of all the women in the novel are a symbol of their character. **Bikə** (*Bike* means lady, lord's wife in ancient Turkish), **Bəyim** (*Beyim* means lady, lord's daughter in ancient Turkish) – represent ladyhood, **Sənəm** (*Senem*) – beauty, **Çiçək** (*Chichek* means flower in ancient Turkish), **Çəmən** (*Chemen* means meadow in ancient Turkish) - represent devotion to nature, **Ayla** – courage. In addition, the work uses female names such as **Aşaxanım** (*Ashakhanum*), **Qızbəs** (*Qizbes*), **Ağca xatun** (*Akhca khatun*), **Fatma**, **Gülöyşə** (*Gyuloyshe*).

The names chosen by Mevlud Suleymanli for the male characters in the work are not accidental. The names of the sons of the ancient people who migrated with Dede are also ancient Turkic words – **İmir**, **Bəkil** (*Bekil*), **Beyrək** (*Beyrak*), **Göyüş** (*Goyush*), etc. The Ganig generation, which could not accept the Karakallas in the village they moved to, also has ancient roots. Perhaps these two generations were once one. The names of the representatives of this generation are also ancient Turkic names: **Qanıq ağa** (*Ganig agha*), **Dursun**, **Beybək** (*Beybek*), **Qutluq** (*Kutluk*), etc. The flow of history continues in the Koch village. A new era, a new culture, a new religion greet the people of the village. The new names given are names that are foreign to Karakalla and Ganig villages: **İsmayıl** (*Ismail*), **Vəli** (*Veli*), **Şamil** (*Shamil*), **İslam** (*Islam*), **Məhəmməd** (*Muhammad*), **Səməd** (*Samad*),

Kərəm (*Kerem*). Those who bear these names are slowly starting to move away from their ancient customs and traditions. A little more time passes. Maybe 5 years, maybe 50, maybe 500, maybe 1000. New names have moved to the Migration village: **Ləmsə Qurd Qurtan ağa** (*Lemsa Kurt Kurtan agha*), **Qabriella** (*Gabriella*), **Ella**, **Maks** (*Max*). These names are the names of foreign forces, distant forces that this country can never accept, that have come to exploit them. Unable to make a nest in this very land, they leave here after a short time. However, the budding loves and the growing hopes are content with watching from the sidelines. Then, with another migration, a blond, green-eyed representative of the Karakalla – Aman – opens his eyes to the world in the middle of Europe.

The language of the work uses not only personal names, but also nicknames. **Dədə** (*Dede* means grandpa or great father in turkic languages) and **Nənə** (*Nene* means grandma or great mother in turkic languages), whose names are unknown to us, are ancient connoisseurs of two peoples who migrated and lived in that region. The nickname **Ağ** (*Agh* means white in Azerbaijani) was given to a camel and a shepherd. The nameless child, who was wrinkled like a fist due to illness as a child, was called **Yumuğ** (the pronunciation of the word "Yumug" is close to the pronunciation of the word "Yumruq" that means fist). When he grew up, he became a strong and dashing man and was named **Aman**. The ancient Turks would not give names to boys unless they showed some heroism. This tradition can also be seen in the epic "The Book of Dede Korkut".

The work uses various family and folk names: **Qanıq evi** (*Ganig house*) – **Qanıqoğlu** (*Ganigoghlu*: son of Ganig), **Qarakəllələr** (*Karakelles*), **Oğuzlar** (*Oghuzs*), **Çirpan evi** (*Chirpan house*) – **Çirpanoğlu** (*Chirpanoglu*: son of Chirpan), **Qoşqar evi** (*Qoshgar house*) – **Qoşqaroğlu** (*Qoshgaroglu*: son of Qoshgar), **Qaraoğlan uşağı** (*child of Garaoghlan*), **Sakatlar** (*Sakats*), **Qaracalar** (*Karajas*), **Qaydovərliilər** (*Qaydavarlis*), **Motallar** (*Motals*), **Qazaxlar** (*Kazakhs*), **Bəylərliilər** (*Beylerlis*), **Bocallar** (*Bojals*), etc.

Religious names such as **Allah** and **Tanrı** (*God*) are also used in the work in accordance with the times of migration.

The work uses geographical names such as **Ağoğlan dağı** (*Aghoglan Mountain*), **Oğuz bazarı** (*Oghuz Bazaar*), **Axçalı** (*Akhchaly*), **Ağçallı** (*Agchally*), **Əyriqar** (*Ayrigar*), **Qarayazı meşəsi** (*Garayazi Forest*), **Yemlik dağı** (*Yemlik Mountain*), **Qaraxac** (*Garakhaj*), **Qara dəniz** (*Black Sea*), **Qılnc düzənlik** (*Sword Plain*), **Sarıyal yol** (*Sariyal Road*), **Bibiqaya** (*Bibigaya*), **Naltoken**, **Russia**, **Caucasus**, and **Europe**.

Conclusion

The work "Koch" – "Migration" does not take place in a single geographical space. It is not clear where this migration came from and where it settled. However, we understand that the events took place in the Oghuz region, in the Caucasus. If we look at history, we will see that since ancient times, local Caspian

Turks settled in this geography, and later there were migrations of new tribes from Central Asia. The Turks mingled and mixed. After the emergence of the Islamic religion, Islamic culture became influential in the geography. During the reign of Tsarist Russia, artificial struggles were created between the peoples of the Caucasus, neighboring and fraternal peoples were killed by each other. For a while, people from Europe were even moved to the Caucasus. German villages were created in the Caucasus. At this time, children were born from the marriages of Germans and Caucasians whose appearance was different from both peoples. The author describes all these historical facts without offending any state, people, or political actor. Therefore, real place names are rarely found in the work. Because "Migration" is not the migration of a single people, a single geography. The novel "Migration" describes the story of the migration of any people who have strayed from their national values. Movlud Suleymanli, through his work "Kock" (Migration) and the names he uses in the work, calls on humanity not to forget itself, its identity, culture, and history. The specific names chosen by the author in his language are diverse and carry ancient history, tradition, and ethnographic colors.

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